

THE IMPACT OF EFFECTIVE STOCK MANAGEMENT ON THE PROFITABILITY OF THE HOSPITALITY OPERATIONS (A CASE OF CHELSEA HOTEL ABUJA)

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines effective stock management and its impact on the profitability of the hospitality operations. A sound and dynamic stock management strategy is indispensable in contemporary time where aggressive competition for survival is the common business trend coupled with rapid increase in technological acceleration. Secondary sources of data collection were employed to get relevant information. The result reveals that effective stock management is inevitably the bedrock upon which every successful hotel establishment is established. Furthermore, the research shows that ineffective stock management consequently results in epileptic revenue yield in hotel industry. Various recommendations on how to achieve the objective of this research work were also highlighted.

KEYWORDS: Stock, Management, Effective, Profitability.

INTRODUCTION

Contemporary Nigerian hospitality industry is characterized with poor stock management and control. This has automatically resulted in high cost of materials with direct effect on revenue factors such as false documentation, frauds, lack of adequate storage facilities and the use of quacks and non professionals in This sector has also been discovered To have affected sound stock management in hotels and fast food establishment nationwide.

In addition, poor purchasing and over buying of materials most especially the perishable items by some establishment greatly hinders effective store management in the hospitality sector thereby resulting in poor yield and quality products which consequently affects the desired profit Target [8]. Wastages are bound to occur as a result of excessive storage. Goods such as perishable foodstuff, inadequate ventilation, in the

store room, moving stock, incorrect storage temperature, exposure of food materials to vermin are other causes of deterioration [1] also there are also consumable stocks such as office stationary. Economy in the use of office stationary should be the target of the hold staff [7].

Effective stock management is the bedrock upon which every successful hospitality organization is built. A sound, as well as dynamic stock management system is an indispensable prerequisite to achieving maximum profitability in the hospitality industry. Stock management is the basic foundation on which any hold establishment which is profit oriented is established.

It is very important to emphasize that one of the most pervasive problem or difficulty challenging the hospitality industry currently and tremendously crippling its sales and maximum profitability is the system of stock management adopted. Stock management cannot be fully comprehended without making mention of various control systems that are adoptable in the hospitality industry. Hence, Lillicrap [5] revealed that the type of control system employed might vary from one establishment to another depending on its size and the complexity of its operations. He further stated that a large establishment is expected to use detail records to achieve the required dock control, while a small establishment with a high degree of personal supervision by the proprietor and keeping small stock will require very little store records.

Literature Review

The hospitality industry provides services to people who are away from their own personal or private abode regardless of the time. The demand for these services as part of an overall experience in the hospitality sector has developed tremendously.

According to Lockwood [6], hospitality is the people business of providing security physical and psychological comfort for rewards. This definition covers not just the commercial or profit sector of the hospitality industry where payment is made directly by the customer but also the cost or non-profit sector where payment is made indirectly.

The Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary defines Hospitality as the act or practice of being hospitable; the reception and entertainment of guests, visitors or strangers with liberality or goodwill. Recent editions of the Oxford English Dictionary recognizes the occurrence of commercial hospitality in a room, suites, hotel, T.V Studio, set aside for the entertainment of guests with drink. From this definition, the outer primary interacting element is that of the social relationship fostered by the warm, friendly welcoming, courteous, open, generous behaviour of the host creating the hospitable social environment's This promotes the positive feeling of security and comfort created by the physical structure design, decor and location of the facility, the provision of accommodation facilities to sleep, relax and wash together with the supply of food, beverages and entertainment.

Jessop [2] revealed that stock management is the activities of determining the range of quantities of materials which should be stocked and the regulations of receipts and issuance of these materials. In other words, it is the operation of continuously arranging flows of materials so that stock balances are adequate to support the current rate of consumption. He further asserted that the reasons for stock taking are as follows:

- To reveal any weakness in the system for the custody and control of stock.
- To verify the accuracy of stock record.
- To disclose or expose the possibility of fraud, theft or loss.
- To support the value of stock shown in the balance sheet by physical verification.

This implies that stock management is the means by which materials of the correct quality and quantity are available and when required with due regard to economy in storage and ordering cost, purchase prices and working capital [3]. Hence, stock management could also be seen as the act of keeping materials raw or finished goods and proper administrating of those materials to meet immediate or future requirements.

Kinton [4] reported that stock is the supply of goods that is available for sales in a shop or store. As a result, excessive stock and immobilization of large amount of capital make it impossible to maintain profitable rates of return capital. According to Kelvin [3] the internet stock management is the function of understanding the stock mix of a company and different demands on the stock. The demands are influenced by both external and internal factors and are balanced by the creation of purchase order request to keep supplies at a reasonable or prescribed level.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

For the purpose of this research work a twenty-five (25) item questionnaire was designed and employed. Simple percentage was used to analyses the response. The population of the study comprised both staff and guest of Chelsea 1-latet Abuja. In all 400 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to subject through simple random sampling. Out of this number only 350 were retrieved. This is an indication that reasonable percentage of the responses became the basic for the data analysis used in this research work.

Data Presentation and Analysis

The data presented and analysed below reflects the information obtained from the questionnaire used.

Research Assumptions

Any of the questions that draws up to 30% and above of the total points obtainable is considered answered.

Table 1: Summary of questionnaire items.

Items		No of Respondent		Percentage
2	Is the size of operation, size of stock, shelf life of materials put into consideration before stock purchasing	Yes	250	85%
		No	30	10%
		No Idea	20	7%
4	Stock prices are becoming expensive due to dwindling economic market situation, hence there is proper accountability for damages	Yes	200	87%
		No	10	4%
		No Idea	20	9%

Source: Field Survey 2013

From Table 1, the information shows that 250 respondent representing 85% said the hotel normally puts into consideration the size of operation, size of stock, shelf life of materials before purchasing stock, while 30 respondent representing 10% said it is not true, but 20 respondent representing 7% did not say anything about it. Similarly, 200 respondents representing 87% asserted that as a result dwindling economic market situations there is proper accountability for damages, 10 respondent representing 4% responded negatively, while 20 respondent representing 9% had no idea.

To answer this question, items 2 and 4 of the questionnaires were used as shown in the above table. The summation of the overall “YES” option point is

$$85+87 = 172 \text{ X } 100 \text{ 530} = 32\%$$

This question has scored above 30% of the total points obtained for acceptance.

As such, the question is answered in the affirmative.

Table 2: Summary of Questionnaire items.

Items		No of Respondent		Percentage
2	Has purchasing order delivery note, invoice, bin card, requisition note, the goods received note and so on enhanced stock control in the hotel	Yes	250	52%
		No	30	31%
		No Idea	20	17%
4	Can the hotel staffs use all control documents enumerated in item (7) effectively with little or no supervision	Yes	200	71%
		No	10	16%
		No Idea	20	13%

Source: Field Survey 2013

From the Table 2, 150 respondent representing 52% said that purchasing order, delivery notes, invoice bin card, requisition notes, the goods received note and so on has enhanced stock management in the hotel, while 90 respondent representing 31% said it is not true, but 50 respondent representing 17% did not respond. Also, 220 respondent representing 71% agreed that all their staffs concerned can effectively use stock control documents with little or no supervision, while 50 respondent representing 16% disagreed on this issue but 40 respondent representing 13% made no comment.

To answer this question items 7 and 9 of the questionnaire were used as shown in the above table. The summation of the overall "YES" option points is $150 + 220 = 370$ X $100 / 600 = 62\%$.

This question has scored above 30% of the total points obtained for acceptance. As such, the question is considered answered in the affirmative.

Question 3: Has proper stock management boosted the hotels profitability in recent time? overstocking or understocking because they purchase on demand. However, there have been cases of fraud and spoilage due to incorrect storage of stock items as well as pest infestation.

CONCLUSION

It is pertinent to note that stock management is indispensable in contemporary time where aggressive competition is the order of the day. The viability of the hospitality business depends solely on the effectiveness of stock management system adopted. Through stock control records, the management of any hospitality establishment can easily ascertain the financial status of its organization, fraudulent acts and other material misconducts are usually checkmated as well as minimized if not totally reduced to the barest minimum through dynamic stock management, in a nutshell, no effective stock management, no income viability.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Proper control of stock should be done to avoid pest infestation.
- Stock items should be properly arranged and stored to prevent excessive wastages.
- The store environment should be properly fumigated to prevent pest attack.

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